

D5.5 Mini housing design & manufacturing

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-LC-BAT-10-2020 GA No. 963540
Project title	Manufacturing and assembly of modular and reusable EV battery for environment-friendly and lightweight mobility
Duration of the project	2021 – 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP5
Document due Date:	31.05.2022
Actual date of delivery	06.09.2022
Leader of this deliverable	ASAS
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0	02/08/2021	Carlos Espinar	Creation of document
1	18/07/2022	İlyas Artunç Sarı	Manufacturing procedures are added
2	31/07/2022	Alberto Gómez	Deliverable review
3	02/09/2022	Carlos Espinar	Revision
4	06/09/2022	Eduard Piqueras	Revision and Submission

Executive summary

This deliverable includes:

- The design of the mini housing
- The manufacturing process of the mini housing

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List of abbreviations

<i>WPs</i>	<i>Work Packages</i>
<i>BP</i>	<i>Battery Pack</i>
<i>DC</i>	<i>Direct Chill</i>

Introduction

Despite the fact that D5.5 is classified as a deliverable of the type "demonstrator", this report aims to provide a brief report gathering all the information concerning the design and the manufacturing of the mini housing demonstrator.

The work on the mini housing is carried out within Task 5.5 "Battery Pack housing design".

1. MINI HOUSING DESIGN

The idea behind manufacturing a miniaturized housing is to study the weak points of the housing structure while saving time and materials (related to MARBEL specific objectives SO5/SO9) and improving the safety and quality of the test methods (MARBEL specific objective SO8).

The modularity goal of MARBEL is addressed by designing modular profiles (see “D5.4 *Optimized profile geometry*”). Therefore, in order to prove these modular aspects of the battery, the mini-housing will be manufactured as an exact replica of the final battery housing.

This decision implies that the 3 dies used to manufacture the mini-housing' extruded profiles will be the same that will be used to manufacture the final MARBEL battery housing. This will permit to save cost and time associated to the development and use of a unique die for every different design.

The following picture shows the current MARBEL Battery housing design.

Figure 1. MARBEL Battery housing design.

As it is shown in Figure 2, the current design has 9 bottom profiles and 8 lateral profiles.

Figure 2. Lidless BP with the number of housing profiles.

For the bottom profiles only two dies will be developed, since profile number 9, where the junction box is placed, is wider than the rest (see Figure 3). For the lateral profiles, one die is needed to manufacture the 8 profiles.

Figure 3. Two different profiles for the bottom plate.

Since the physical tests that will be applied to the mini-housing do not require the need of a functional battery within, all internal components will be substituted by dummies of the exact weight (this is necessary in the acceleration tests).

Now that the design and distribution of the housing have been explained, the following pictures show the mini-housing that will be manufactured.

Figure 4. MARBEL mini-housing.

Figure 5. Lidless MARBEL mini-housing.

The current MARBEL Battery Pack dimensions are 2220 x 1610 mm², and the mini-housing is scaled 1:¼ approximately. Therefore, the mini-housing dimension are 830 x 500 mm².

2.

MINI HOUSING MANUFACTURING PROCEDURES

2.1 OVERALL MANUFACTURING PROCEDURES

Billet production in diameters suitable for extrusion is carried out by DC casting method. This is the first stage of the profile production. Alloying elements are melted in industrial furnaces and then the casting process is started. Figure 6 shows the DC Casting furnace.

Figure 6. DC Casting furnace.

Homogenization has been done arduously. DC cast billets homogenized between 450-550°C so that homogenization of the microstructure was done. This process prevents the non-uniformity of mechanical properties throughout the profiles.

Extrusion die is another important part for extrusion. In dieshop, ASAS can produce extrusion dies from bulk slab hot working tool steel with machining operations. Dies are designing according to desired profiles.

Figure 7. Dieshop

Die designs are made with SolidWorks CAD software.

Figure 8. Die design with SolidWorks

Figure 9 represents that how hot working tool steel is machined.

Figure 9. Die machining

Main parameters that effect the product are billet temperature and extrusion speed. The cast 7 m long aluminium logs were cut into 0,8-1,2m long billets. Billets then were heated up to designated temperatures in gas and induction ovens sequentially. Then these billets were extruded with presses that differ from 13MNs to 62MNs of force. As mentioned before, ASAS' 62MN Press is the largest extrusion press in Turkey. See Figure 10.

Figure 10. Extrusion press.

Die design has crucial effect in extrusion process directly effecting the outlet temperature and shape of the profiles making it one of the most important parameters of extrusion. Die design effects the exit temperature and exit temperature directly effects the mechanical properties of extruded profile also positions of die bearings effects profile since position of the die bearings determine the seamweld position.

In case of mechanical properties of profiles were not met at press exit heat treatment were carried accordingly. The mentioned heat treatments can be done to 6xxx alloys to improve their mechanical properties since they are age hardenable alloys.

2.2 PROFILE MANUFACTURING PROCEDURES

As explained before, the length of the profile can be cut as desired, and just one die to manufacture different profiles is needed. See Figure 11.

Figure 11. Same section of the bottom profiles, different lengths.

Figure 12. Same section of the lateral profile, different length and finishing.

The procedure is the same for the rest of the profiles.

Summarizing, for this housing, 3 dies will be manufactured. One for the bottom profiles See pictures below.

Figure 13. Picture of the profile 8 section.

Figure 14. Picture of the profile 9 section.

Figure 15. Picture of the lateral profiles.

Once the parts are extruded, they will be cut. Moreover, for the lateral profiles, some edges will be machined to fit with the rest of the parts.

Figure 16. Top view of the lateral profile and the machined areas.

Figure 17. Lateral view of the lateral profile with the machined area.

Regarding the lid, due to the reduced dimension and the preliminary test, just a flat aluminum sheet will be manufactured as shown in Figure 4.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of this deliverable are:

The mini-housing and the housing share the same dies to prove modularity and manufacturing cost reduction when producing batteries with different dimensions.

The physical demonstrator will be manufactured once the design of the profiles is frozen. See "*D5.4 Optimized profile geometry*" for further explanation.

Three dies will be used to manufacture the mini-housing and the same dies will be used to manufacture the housing of the Battery Pack..

The mini-housing will be scaled approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ of the real housing.